

ECOBULK

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

GA NUMBER: 730456

Final Conference

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Revision History

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report will make a record of the planning and the results of the Final Conference of the Ecobulk project.

The final conference was held online due to the persisting uncertainties of the pandemic situation. The event itself had the goal to present the major findings of the project to a relevant stakeholder audience.

The planning for the event tried to take into account the amount of work done for the project in comparison to the time an audience might want to spend learning about the project. Even so the event was planned for a total of 4 hours, divided into two 2-hour sessions.

The first session would focus on the design framework and prototypes/ demonstrators of the project.

The second session would start off with the business cases for the demonstrations, and then present the materials, and other enabling technologies such as reverse logistics and lifecycle thinking.

At the end of the event a question and discussion session was planned for the audience to ask any questions and to be able to talk about the legacy of the project and future of any work carried forward by the partners.

The first session had a total of 89 registrations, of which 52 attended. There were 46 messages and 6 questions asked through the event system.

The second session had a total of 87 registrations, of which 41 attended. There were 51 messages and 4 questions asked through the event system.

Both sessions were recorded and available through the Ecobulk YouTube channel:

<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLgnp2jd4x9JvBSJ9EjM3YTtBVPcArE76K>

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1 PROGRAM

The program for the final conference was conceived to focus on the prototypes as this was thought to be the most salient part of the project that would attract the most attention. Based on the prototypes audience members might decide they want to stay to learn about the rest. The design framework was placed first in the program, after a general introduction to the project. It would after all make sense to discuss general design principles and then see them implemented in the demonstration products. The demonstrations were then given an hour to present the results, divided into 3 blocks, one for each industrial sector (automotive, construction and furniture). After that there would be a break.

The second session was planned to start with the business models, as this is another topic that is usually popular in the circular economy stakeholders. This could be used as hook to make sure people come back after the break. It does of course also make sense to discuss the business models after having presented the prototypes, as it gives the demonstrations more of a context to show their feasibility and/or viability in economic terms.

Afterwards time was made to include information on the so-called enabling technologies and developments that make the circular model possible. Here it was not possible to include everything that was done in the 4.5 year project, and so a selection of the most salient content was selected for presentation. This included the Materials, Collection and Sorting and Stakeholder platform that all play central roles in the circular lifecycle. Then there was time for LifeCycle Thinking that was important to show the sustainability of the prototypes and demonstrations.

Finally, it was thought appropriate to finish with a small discussion on the future of the work, and the legacy of the project perhaps in the wider sense of being able to demonstrate circularity for composites.

The plan was also to record the final event sessions so that these could be made available publicly through the website and the YouTube channel so that anyone could watch the presentations of the results of the project.

Program

The poster features a central circular graphic with the Ecobulk logo and the word 'ECOBULK' in the center. The graphic is overlaid on a background of a hand holding a small plant seedling. The circular graphic contains icons for a sun, a water drop, a leaf, a gear, and a recycling symbol, all connected by arrows in a circular path. The text 'Ecobulk' is underlined, and 'Final Conference' is in a large, bold font. Below that, the subtitle 'Circular Composites in Automotive, Furniture & Construction' is in a smaller, italicized font. At the bottom, the date and time '26 NOVEMBER 2021 09h-13h CEST' are displayed in a yellow font.

Ecobulk
Final Conference
*Circular Composites in Automotive,
Furniture & Construction*

26 NOVEMBER 2021
09h-13h CEST

Demonstrating Circularity for Bulky Composite Products in Automotive, Furniture & Construction Sectors

09:00 – **Welcome & agenda** | Jose Uribe, ISWA

09:05 – **Project Overview & Introduction** | Luis Romeral, UPC.

09:20 – **Circular Design** | Ruud Balkenende, [TuDelft](#).

09:40 – **Demonstrations**

- Overview | Markku Vilkki, [Conenor](#).
- Construction | Markku Vilkki, [Conenor](#).
- Automotive: Central Console Parts - 2K Injection | Mario Ordonez, Maier.
- Automotive: [Vianova](#) Hydrogen Fuel Cell Vehicle | John Jostins, [Microcab](#).
- Furniture: Modular Bedroom Concept | Giovanni Tosi, Moretti Compact.
- Furniture: Outdoor and Other Concepts | Emilie Bossanne, FCBA.

Break 10:40 – 11:00

11:00 – **Business Models** | Olivia Bertham, [Oakdene Hollins](#).

11:20 – **Innovative materials**

- Overview & [Airlaid Nonwovens](#) | Daniele Spinelli, NEXT.
- LFTs and Natural Fibers | Chris Hare, [Coventive](#).
- Particle Board Binders | Anna Furberg, [Akzonobel](#).

11:40 – **Circularity Enabling Technologies**

- Overview | Victor Martinez, UPC.
- Decision Support System, Stakeholder platform & Quality Assurance System | Victor Martinez, UPC.

12:00 – **Collection & Recovery**

- Overview & strategies | Sergio Guerri, ITENE
- Automotive | Sergio Guerri, ITENE
- Sorting Technologies | Lisa [Hoflechner](#), [Tomra](#).

12:20 – **LCA Thinking**

- Key Issues in Repair Systems, Recycling and Social Aspects | Emilie Bossanne, FCBA.
- Key Learnings of LC Thinking in Automotive, Furniture and Construction | Emilie Bossanne, FCBA

12:40 – **Discussion on the Future and Legacy**

13:00 – **Wrap-up and Close**

End of Event

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020
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2 PROMOTION

The final conference was promoted regularly through social media and newsletters to get an audience. The partners were also asked to spread the news in their own networks, and share the posts with links to information and registration pages.

Website Page

A website page was made that linked straight to the registration page:

"ECOBULK: Demonstrating Circularity for Bulky Composite Products in Automotive, Furniture & Construction Sectors".

The ECOBULK project will be making the case that **circularity for composites** is not only possible but can also be **appealing and profitable**. Realized production prototypes in the automotive, furniture and construction industry will be presented along with the enabling technologies that **allow the circular lifecycle to take place**. This includes the following developments:

- New materials,
- Circular Design Guidelines,
- Business models,
- Decision support system,
- Quality assurance,
- Other supporting technologies and processes.

Join us for the project results conference, register now and help us celebrate our achievements, share our lessons learnt and explore the way forward.

Mailing List Invitations

The mailing list that was built up over the last 4 years was the first and best place to start the promotion. The list contains 200+ addresses of people we know are/were definitely interested in the project at some stage. To make sure the information about

the event was not lost among other items, the invitation was sent out by itself, and a reminder was sent afterwards when the program was finalised.

Completed Campaign • Nov 8

Personal Invitation | Demonstrating Circularity for Bulky Composite Products Email

Clicks 14.7% • Opens 33.5%

Completed Campaign • Nov 18

Program Ready! | Demonstrating Circularity for Bulky Composite Products Email

Clicks 7.9% • Opens 23%

Newsletter

The final newsletter sent out a couple of days after the final consortium meeting included the link and invitation to register for the final event. The newsletter itself focused on the business models and enabling technologies to be able to attract those that might be interested in those aspects rather than the prototypes/demonstrators.

Completed Campaign • Nov 25

Newsletter M54 Email

Clicks 6.7% • Opens 25.4%

Social Media Posts

The social media posts were used to attract more attendees. There was also an even created on LinkedIn to get more exposure to a professional audience.

More posts were also done on the day to try to get more attention and perhaps even some last minute registrations:

Page posts

Promotional Banners

LIVE WEBINAR

Demonstrating Circularity for Bulky Composite Products in Automotive, Furniture & Construction Sectors.

 November 26

 09:00-13:00 CET

“A design that does not take into account the end-of-life is not complete.”

Ruud Balkenende
Design Work Package leader

For LinkedIn:

Final Conference
Circularity for Composites Products and Materials

Automotive | Furniture | Construction

 ECOBULK

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3 RESULTS

During the run up to the event there were a total of 89 registrations to attend the event. In the first session 52 of those actually attended the event. During the first session there were 46 chat messages sent and 6 questions posed through the system.

89 registrants **52 attendees** **46 messages** **6 questions**

The attendees funnel shows how many people landed on the registration page and what percentage of those actually registered for the event.

The progression of the registrations shows peaks that coincide with some of the promotional activities.

The recording of the first session on the event system, accessible only to those who registered, was watched 11 times. Of those, 4 were from people who did not attend the event at all, which in principle should then be added to the number of people who watched the presentations.

The second session recordings were watched 9 times, 6 of which from people who did not attend the event (hints at the fact the event was too long!).

4 PROCEEDINGS

As part of the legacy, it was also decided to put all of the presentations together as a sort of conference proceedings document that could be made available next to the video recordings. Both of these have been made available on the website, on the Final Conference page.

<https://www.ecobulk.eu/news/ecobulk-final-event/>

▲ Presentations

First part: [slides](#)

Second part: [slides](#)

▲ Recording

[ECOBULK Demonstrating circularity for composites in automotive, furniture and construction Part 1](#)

Session 1: Introduction, Circular Design, Prototypes & Demonstrations

[ECOBULK Demonstrating circularity for composites in automotive, furniture and construction Part 2](#)

Session 2: Business Models, Materials, Enabling Technologies, Collection & Recovery, LCA Thinking, Discussion on Future and Legacy

▲ Program

Full program available [here](#).

The Recordings are available also on YouTube:

<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLgnp2jd4x9JvBSJ9EjM3YTtBVPCArE76K>